

Spectrophotometric Study of the Reaction of Osmium with Promethazine Hydrochloride

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Promethazine hydrochloride is proposed as a new reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of microgram amounts of osmium. It forms a red coloured species with osmium(VIII) or osmium(VI) at room temperature in hydrochloric acid medium. The red species exhibits maximum absorbance at 515 nm. Beer's law is valid over the concentration range, 0.2-4.8 ppm for osmium(VIII) and 0.16-6.0 ppm for osmium(VI). The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is 0.021 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for osmium(VIII) and 0.015 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for osmium(VI). The effects of time, temperature, acidity, order of addition of reagents, reagent concentration and diverse ions are reported.

THE authors reported the use of promethazine hydrochloride, PH, 10-(2-dimethylaminopropyl) phenothiazine hydrochloride for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II)¹ and ruthenium(III)². The present work describes PH as a sensitive reagent for the rapid spectrophotometric determination of osmium(VIII) and osmium(VI). The proposed method offers the advantages of simplicity, sensitivity, reasonable stability and wider range of determination without the need for heating or extraction.

Experimental

Beckman Model DB Spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm silica cells was used for all absorbance measurements.

Standard Os(VIII) and Os(VI) solutions

A stock solution of osmium(VIII) was prepared from osmium tetroxide (M/s Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) in 0.2M sodium hydroxide. The solution was standardised iodometrically³. Standard solution of osmium(VI) was prepared from potassium osmate (J.M.C.) in doubly distilled water. The stock solutions were further diluted to give standard solutions of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

Promethazine hydrochloride solution

A 0.2% aqueous solution of PH (May & Baker) was prepared and stored in a refrigerator. The reagent solution was stable for about one month.

Other reagents

The solutions of acids and diverse ions of suitable concentrations were prepared in double distilled water using analytical grade reagents.

Procedure for the determination of osmium(VIII) or osmium(VI)

An aliquot of the stock solution containing 5 to 120 μg of osmium(VIII) or 4 to 150 μg of osmium(VI) was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask. 10 ml of 7.5M hydrochloric acid and 4 ml of 0.2% PH solution were added and the solution was diluted to the mark with doubly distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 515 nm after standing 15 minutes against a reagent blank prepared in the same way. The amount of osmium in the sample solution was then deduced from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

PH forms a red coloured species which is believed to be a radical cation with osmium(VIII) or osmium(VI) in hydrochloric acid medium at room temperature ($27^\circ \pm 1^\circ$). Osmium(IV) does not give any coloured product with PH. The sensitivity of the reaction and stability of the colour in four acids (3N) are in the order of $\text{HCl} > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 > \text{HAc}$. Although the colour development is initially rapid, a period of 15, 25, 45 and 50 minutes is required to reach the maximum intensity of colour for osmium(VIII) and osmium(VI) in HCl, H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and HAc respectively. The absorbance values remain constant for 45, 20, 15 and 10 minutes for osmium(VIII) and 35, 15, 10 and 5 minutes for osmium(VI) in 3N HCl, H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and HAc respectively. Hence hydrochloric acid medium was chosen for all subsequent studies.

Optimum acid range

Maximum absorbance is achieved in 2.0-4.0M hydrochloric acid for both osmium(VIII) and osmium(VI). Below 2.0M acid concentration the development of red colour is slow. The reagent is slowly oxidised at acidities higher than 4.0M. Nitric acid or any other medium containing oxidising species cannot be used as it oxidises PH to a red coloured species.

Absorbance curves

The absorption spectra of PH, osmium(VIII) and red species are shown in Fig. 1. The red species exhibits maximum absorbance at 514-518 nm. The absorption spectra of PH and osmium(VIII) or osmium(VI) show that they do not absorb at this wavelength. Subsequent studies were made at 515 nm.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of reagent blank, osmium (VIII) and red species. 1. Reagent blank; 2. Osmium (VIII) and 3. Red species (Os=4 ppm, HCl=3N).

Effect of varying reagent concentrations

A 16-fold molar excess of the reagent is required in order to obtain the maximum intensity of colour. The optimum amount of the reagent is 4 ml of 0.2% PH solution in a final volume of 25 ml.

Adherence to Beer's law and optimum range

Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 0.2-4.8 ppm of osmium(VIII) and 0.16-6.0 ppm of osmium(VI). The optimum concentration range for the effective spectrophotometric determination as evaluated by Ringbom's method^{4,5} is 1.0-4.4 ppm for osmium(VIII) and 1.0-5.0 ppm for osmium(VI).

Sensitivity and Molar absorptivity

For $\log I_0/I = 0.001$, the sensitivity of the reaction as calculated from Beer's law data is $0.021 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for osmium(VIII) and $0.015 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for osmium(VI). The respective molar absorptivities are $8.9 \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1.23 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 515 nm.

Order of addition of reagents

It is found that there is no appreciable change in the absorbance or in colour intensity of the red species if the order of addition of reagents is varied.

Effect of temperature

The red species formed by osmium(VIII) or osmium(VI) with PH is stable over the temperature range 4-40° as shown by the constant absorbance readings.

Effect of diverse ions

The effect of anions and cations which often accompany osmium(VIII) are studied. The results are summarised in Table 1. Efforts to increase the tolerance limit of cations by the addition of masking agents were unsuccessful.

TABLE—1. TOLERANCE LIMIT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF 3 PPM OF OSMIUM(VIII)

Ion added	Tolerance limit, ppm	Ion added	Tolerance limit, ppm
F ⁻	1100	Fe ²⁺	4.0
Cl ⁻	7850	Co ²⁺	100.0
Br ⁻	1870	Ni ²⁺	585.0
I ⁻	5	Cu ²⁺	35.0
NO ₃ ⁻	2065	Ru ²⁺	0.5
PO ₄ ³⁻	1375	Rh ²⁺	12.0
SO ₄ ²⁻	1000	Pd ²⁺	0.5
CH ₃ COO ⁻	5345	Ir ²⁺	11.0
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	950	Pt ²⁺	10.0
EDTA	4720	Au ³⁺	0.5

Sample solutions containing $4 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of osmium(VIII) or osmium(VI) prepared by the standard procedure gave a relative error of $\pm 0.7\%$ and standard deviation of 0.002.

Determination of osmium in alloys

Synthetic mixtures corresponding to osmiridium alloy were prepared and the osmium content was determined following the standard procedure. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE—2. DETERMINATION OF OSMIUM IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES CORRESPONDING TO OSMIRIDIUM ALLOY.

Os(VIII) taken, ppm	Ir (III) added, ppm	Os(VIII) found, ppm	Standard deviation, ppm
1.2	0.3	1.196	0.004
2.4	0.6	2.394	0.003
3.6	0.9	3.592	0.002
4.8	1.2	4.790	0.003

*The amount of osmium (VIII) found is based on ten determinations.

The sensitivity of the proposed method is found to be more than that of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole⁶, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole⁷, 1-carbamidino-3-methyl-5-pyrazolene⁸, acenaphthenequinone monoxime⁹ and rubeanic acid¹⁰ which have been proposed as sensitive spectrophotometric reagents for osmium(VIII).

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